

ETHICS AND LEGALITY

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Legality can be termed as the state of being lawful or unlawful in a given jurisdiction or observance of or attachment to the law, or contract, agreement, or act that is consistent with the law. In the healthcare context, legality refers to the observance of the federal, state, and local laws, rules, regulations, and other jurisprudence by healthcare providers, subscribers, and vendors to the patients and healthcare services delivery.

Ethics, on the other hand, refers to moral principles affecting decision making and conduct of people with the aim of maximizing good actions and minimizing harmful ones by systemizing, defending, and recommending right and wrong conduct concepts. In the healthcare context, ethics refers to a set of moral principles, beliefs, and values guiding decision and choice making about healthcare on the basis of rights and wrongs about rights and duties.

Ethics and laws are similar in certain aspects as both systems aim to prevent the violation of and maintenance of set moral values. The two phenomena guide the conduct and decision making of people in various situations. They both aim to make people lives in harmony and benefit form a community or society that is well regulated. Differences include the fact that whereas ethics emanate from the awareness of people's about wrong and right; laws are created and enforced by governments or political formations. Ethics may also differ from one person to the other since they are based on opinions, but laws draw clear lines between what is legal and what is illegal regardless of the opinions of people. Violation of ethics is not punishable, but the violation of laws is punishable by relevant authorities. An action can be ethically right but unlawful, and in the same way a law can be ethically wrong.

Bibliography

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